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PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL STUDIES OF INTERACTION AND GLASS FORMATION IN THE $\text{As}_2\text{Te}_3\text{-Tl}_2\text{Se}$ SYSTEM

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Abstract

Physicochemical studies of interaction and glass formation in the $\text{As}_2\text{Te}_3\text{-Tl}_2\text{Se}$ system were carried out using the following methods: differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD), microstructural analysis (MSA), and by measuring microhardness and density, T-x was constructed phase diagram. The system is a partially quasi-binary diagonal section of the ternary reciprocal system Tl,As//Se,Te. When the component ratio is 1:1, a quaternary compound of the composition $\text{Tl}_2\text{As}_2\text{SeTe}_3$ is formed, which melts congruently at 270°C. It has been established that the $\text{Tl}_2\text{As}_2\text{SeTe}_3$ compound crystallizes in the tetragonal syngony with lattice parameters: $a=11.47 \text{ \AA}$; $c=9.50 \text{ \AA}$, $z=6$, $\rho_{\text{pucn.}}=7.98 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $\rho_{\text{X-ray}}=8.13 \text{ g/cm}^3$. In the system at room temperature, solid solutions based on As_2Te_3 reach 3.3 mol % Tl_2Se , and solid solutions based on Tl_2Se are practically not established. Under normal conditions, extensive areas of glass formation based on $\text{Tl}_2\text{As}_2\text{SeTe}_3$ were found in the concentration range of 35-70 mol % Tl_2Se .

Introduction

One of the important tasks facing the chemistry and physics of semiconductors is the study of the synthesis and properties of materials consisting of energy converters with photo- and thermoelectric properties for the efficient use of alternative energy sources. Obtaining phase diagrams of the corresponding systems in new semiconductor materials with complex properties is of great importance.

It is known that arsenic chalcogenides and alloys based on them, new complex phases, are materials with photoelectric [1-8], luminescent [9,10], properties widely used in color television, IR optics in memory centres [11-13].

In recent years, chalcogenide fibres [14–19] based on As_2S_3 and As_2Se_3 have been used to transmit light in the mid-IR range and have found application as a compact nonlinear medium allowing Raman amplification [20] and lasing [21]. The As_2Te_3 compound does not form glass under normal conditions, but ternary and quaternary compounds obtained in systems consisting of thallium chalcogenides are glassy and form large areas. The As_2Te_3 compound and the complex phases obtained on its basis are materials with photoelectric properties [22,23]. Many systems involving arsenic and thallium chalcogenides have been studied in the literature [24-27].

The purpose of this work is to study the interaction and glass formation in the $\text{As}_2\text{Te}_3\text{-Tl}_2\text{Se}$ system, as well as the search for new semiconductor phases.

The initial components of the system As_2Te_3 and Tl_2Se are characterized by the following data: The As_2Te_3 compound melts at 381°C and crystallizes in a monoclinic syngony with lattice parameters: $a = 1.4339$; $b = 0.4006$; $c = 0.9873 \text{ nm}$, $\beta = 95^\circ$, sp. gr. C2/m [28]. The Tl_2Se compound melts the open maximum at 390°C and crystallizes in a tetragonal syngony with lattice parameters: $a = 0.854 \text{ nm}$, $c = 0.271 \text{ nm}$, density $\rho = 9.65 \text{ g/cm}^3$ [29].

Experimental part

To study the $\text{As}_2\text{Te}_3\text{-Tl}_2\text{Se}$ system, alloys were synthesized from the As_2Te_3 and Tl_2Se components in evacuated quartz ampoules at a pressure of 0.133 Pa in the temperature range 500-700°C. Then the alloys were homogenized by annealing at 190°C for 540 hours. After homogenization of the alloys, the systems were studied using the methods of physicochemical analysis (DTA, X-ray diffraction, MSA), as well as density and microhardness measurements. Differential thermal analysis of the samples was carried out using a THERMOSCAN-2 device. Al_2O_3 was used as standard, heating rate was 5 deg/min.

X-ray phase analysis was performed on a D2 PHASER X-ray diffractometer. A $\text{CuK}\alpha$ cathode and a

Ni filter were used as irradiators. Microhardness was measured using a PMT-3 metallographic microscope. Microstructural analysis of the alloys was carried out using a MIM-8 microscope.

Results and its discussion

Alloys of the $As_2Te_3-Tl_2Se$ system were synthesized from As_2Te_3 and Tl_2Se components in quartz ampoules evacuated to 0.133 Pa at a temperature of 700-800°C. The melts were cooled slowly at a rate of 150 deg/h. up to 400°C, then at a speed of (50-60) deg/h. Alloys containing 35-70 mol % Tl_2Se is obtained in glassy form. Alloys with a high content of As_2Te_3 are stable in water and air at room temperature; they dissolve in mineral acids HCl, HNO_3 and alkalis NaOH, KOH.

To homogenize the alloys, the $As_2Te_3-Tl_2Se$ systems were annealed at 190, 250 and 300°C for 750 hours. After annealing, the alloys were studied using a set of methods of physicochemical analysis: DTA, XRF, MSA, microhardness and density measurements.

Some physicochemical properties of alloys of the $As_2Te_3-Tl_2Se$ system were studied before and after annealing (Table 1.2). Thermal analysis showed that in the concentration range of 35-70 mol. % Tl_2Se on thermograms of cast alloys a softening temperature of 155-125°C is observed. DTA indicates that with the exception of alloys in the range of 20-80 mol % Tl_2Se all effects, in the thermograms of the obtained alloys, are endothermic and reversible. Glass-crystalline regions are observed in the concentration range of 20-35 mol % Tl_2Se and 70-80 mol % Tl_2Se .

The XRF results also confirm the DTA and MSA data. In the diffraction patterns of alloys of the $As_2Te_3-Tl_2Se$ system in the range of 35-70 mol % Tl_2Se no intense diffraction maxima are observed (Fig. 1). After long-term annealing, softening temperatures disappear from the glass region in the heating curves of the alloys, and intense diffraction reflections appear in the diffraction pattern (Fig. 2). In Fig. 1 shows X-ray diffraction patterns of alloys from the region of glasses of the $As_2Te_3-Tl_2Se$ system containing 30, 50, 60 and 70 mol % Tl_2Se .

Fig.1. X-ray diffraction patterns of alloys from the glass region of the $As_2Te_3-Tl_2Se$ system. 1-40 mol %, 2-50 mol %, 3-60 mol %, 4-70 mol. % Tl_2Se .

A microscopic study of alloys of the $As_2Te_3-Tl_2Se$ system showed that alloys in the concentration range of 35-70 mol % Tl_2Se are glasses, and in the region of 15-35 mol % Tl_2Se and 70-80 mol. % Tl_2Se are glasses with crystalline inclusions. Finally, it was revealed that with slow cooling in the system, the glass formation region based on $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$ extends from 35 to 70 mol % Tl_2Se . Some physicochemical properties of the alloys of the system before and after annealing are given in (Tables 1 and 2). As can be seen from Table 1, the softening temperature T_g of alloys from the glass region, in the concentration range of 20-70 mol % Tl_2Se , varies between 155-125°C. The microhardness of alloys from the glass region varies within the range (810-

850) MPa (Table 1). After prolonged annealing in the concentration range of 35-70 mol % Tl_2Se in thermograms of glassy alloys, the temperature T_g disappears, and the temperatures associated with the liquidus and solidus remain unchanged (Table 2).

This means that after heat treatment, glassy alloys are completely crystallized. As can be seen from table. 1 and 2, the microhardness of alloys from the glass region is greater than from the crystalline state. On the other hand, the density of glassy alloys is lower compared to the density of crystalline alloys. The results obtained are in good agreement with the literature data on the properties of glasses.

Table 1.

Composition, DTA results, microhardness measurements and determinations density of alloys of the As₂Te₃-Tl₂Se system before annealing (S₁- Tl₂As₂SeTe₃), (S₂- Tl₂As₂Se₃Te)

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, g/cm ³	Microhardness, MPa				
As ₂ Te ₃	Tl ₂ Se			α	S ₁	S ₂	Tl ₂ Te	Tl ₂ Se
P=0,15 N								
100	0,0	381	6.23	1650	-	-	-	-
97	3,0	285.365	6.27	1690	-	-	-	-
95	5,0	245.350	6.40	1700	-	-	-	-
90	10	190.340	6.57	1700	-	-	-	-
80	20	155.190.285	6.91	1700	-	-	-	-
75	25	150.90.235	7.08	-	-	-	-	-
70	30	150.190	7.32	Eutec.	Eutec.	-	-	-
65	35	140.190;225	7.42	-	810	-	-	-
60	40	130.190.240	7.60	-	830	-	-	-
55	45	125.190.260	7.76	-	840	-	-	-
50	50	125.270	7.98	-	850	-	-	-
45	55	125.255.265	8.,10	-	850	-	-	-
40	60	125.225.255.260	8.28	-	850	-	-	-
35	65	125.225.245.290	8.45	-	Eutec.	Eutec.	Eutec.	-
30	70	125.225.325	8.63	-	-	980	-	-
25	75	320.350	8.79	-	-	980	550	-
20	80	300.315.345	8.97	-	-	980	560	-
15	85	300.310.340	9,13	-	-	-	-	-
10	90	300.345	9.31	-	-	Eutec.	Eutec.	Eutec.
5.0	95	300.345.365	9.47	-	-	-	-	540
3,0	97	300.345.380	9.55	-	-	-	-	530
0,0	100	390	9.65	-	-	-	-	520

When measuring microhardness, five rows of values were obtained (Tables 1 and 2). After annealing at 190°C for 540 hours (Table 2), microhardness for the gray phase (1650-1700) MPa (α-phase based on As₂Te₃), for the dark phase (730-760) MPa (Tl₂As₂SeTe₃), for light gray phase (980) MPa (Tl₂As₂Se₃Te), for the light phase (550-560) MPa (Tl₂Te) and for the dark gray phase (520-540) MPa (Tl₂Se).

Table 2.

Composition, DTA results, microhardness measurements and determinations densities of alloys of the As₂Te₃-Tl₂Se system after annealing (S₁- Tl₂As₂SeTe₃), (S₂- Tl₂As₂Se₃Te)

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, g/cm ³	Microhardness, MPa				
As ₂ Te ₃	Tl ₂ Se			α	S ₁	S ₂	Tl ₂ Te	Tl ₂ Se
P=0,10 N								
100	0,0	381	6.23	1650	-	-	-	-
97	3,0	285.365	6.27	1690	-	-	-	-
95	5,0	245.350	6.40	1700	-	-	-	-
90	10	190.340	6.57	1700	-	-	-	-
80	20	190.285	6.91	1700	-	-	-	-
75	25	190.235	7.18	-	-	-	-	-
70	30	190	7.40	Eutec.	Eutec.	-	-	-
65	35	190.225	7.52	-	730	-	-	-
60	40	190.240	7.70	-	730	-	-	-
55	45	190.260	7.87	-	740	-	-	-
50	50	270	8.11	-	750	-	-	-
45	55	225.255.265	8.16	-	760	-	-	-
40	60	225.255.260	8.38	-	760	-	-	-
35	65	225.245.290	8.55	-	Eutec.	Eutec.	Eutec.	-
30	70	225.325	8.68	-	-	980	-	-
25	75	320.350	8.79	-	-	980	550	-
20	80	300.315.345	8.97	-	-	980	560	-
15	85	300.310.340	9,13	-	-	-	-	-
10	90	300.345	9.31	-	-	Eutec.	Eutec.	Eutec.
5.0	95	300.345.365	9.47	-	-	-	-	540
3,0	97	300.345.380	9.55	-	-	-	-	530
0,0	100	390	9.65	-	-	-	-	520

The microhardness of the glassy compound $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$ before and after annealing changes noticeably (Tables 1, 2). The state diagram of the As_2Te_3 - Tl_2Se system is shown in Fig. 2. The nature of the chemical interaction in the As_2Te_3 - Tl_2Se and As_2Te_3 - Tl_2S systems is the same. Both systems are partially quasi-binary and represent diagonal sections of the ternary reciprocal systems $As, Tl // Se, Te$ and $As, Tl // S, Te$, respectively.

One chemical compound of the composition $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$ is formed in the system, which melts congruently at $270^\circ C$. The $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$ compounds have a similar character and can be considered derivatives of $Tl_2As_2X_4 = TlAsX_2$. Here, isomorphous substitution of chalcogens occurs.

Fig.2. Phase diagram of the As_2Te_3 - Tl_2Se system.

Fig.3. Diffraction patterns of alloys of the As_2Te_3 - Tl_2Se system. 1- As_2Te_3 , 2-3 mol %, 3-50 mol % ($Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$), 4-100 mol % Tl_2Se .

The existence of the $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$ compound was confirmed by methods of physicochemical analysis (DTA, XRF, MSA, determination of microhardness and density). The XRD results of alloys of the As_2Te_3 - Tl_2Se system are shown in Fig. 3. As can be seen from Fig. 3, the X-ray diffraction pattern of the 1:1 alloy ($Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$) contains diffraction lines that differ from the lines of the original components both in intensity and in the value of interplanar distances (Fig. This indicates the presence of a new phase in the As_2Te_3 - Tl_2Se

system, formed by the reaction: As_2Te_3 - $Tl_2Se = Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$

Interplanar distances and line intensities in the X-ray diffraction patterns of the remaining alloys, excluding the regions of solid solutions, indicate the presence of a mixture of other phases in them. Identification of the powder pattern shows that $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$ crystallizes in the tetragonal syngony with lattice parameters: $a=11.47 \text{ \AA}$; $c=9.50 \text{ \AA}$, $z=6$, density $\rho_{puc}=7.98 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $\rho_{X\text{-ray}}=8.13 \text{ g/cm}^3$. Table 3 shows the crystallographic data of the compound $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$.

Table 3.

Crystallographic data of the compound $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$

No	I, %	$d_{exp}, \text{ \AA}$	$d_{cal}, \text{ \AA}$	h	k	l
1	17	3,7319	3,7920	2	2	1
2	12	3,3903	3,3903	3	1	1
3	57	3,2318	3,1814	3	2	0
4	21	3,1605	3,1670	0	0	3
5	29	3,0780	3,0846	2	2	2
6	96	2,9785	2,9785	3	0	2
7	61	2,9308	2,9501	1	1	3
8	100	2,8665	2,8687	4	0	0
9	14	2,6397	2,6943	3	2	2
10	19	2,5996	2,6011	3	3	1
11	21	2,4295	2,4390	3	0	3
12	17	2,3678	2,3756	0	0	4
13	14	2,1963	2,2947	2	0	4
14	9	2,0498	2,0498	2	2	4
15	14	1,9672	1,9672	5	3	0
16	24	1,8241	1,8176	5	3	2
17	9	1,7841	1,7817	6	2	1
18	9	1,7187	1,7206	2	2	5
19	19	1,6556	1,6502	5	0	4
20	16	1,6393	1,6386	7	0	0

Conclusion

Thus, a state diagram of the As_2Te_3 - Tl_2Se system has been constructed. The system is characterized by the formation of one chemical compound $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$. The $Tl_2As_2SeTe_3$ compound crystallizes in the tetragonal syngony with lattice parameters: $a=11.47 \text{ \AA}$; $c=9.50 \text{ \AA}$, $z=6$, $\rho_{pucn.}=7.98 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $\rho_{X\text{-ray}}=8.13 \text{ g/cm}^3$. It has been established that in the As_2Te_3 - Tl_2Se system based on As_2Te_3 , solid solutions reach 3.3 mol % Tl_2Se . It was revealed that with slow cooling, the boundary of the glass formation region extends from 35 to 70 mol % Tl_2Se . A study of the chemical interaction of thallium chalcogenides with arsenic chalcogenides showed that the alloys exhibit a greater tendency to glass formation. The resulting alloys are compact, with a high content of As_2Te_3 , the color of the alloys has a metallic luster, the remaining alloys are dark brown.

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